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Motor Skills Development among Kindergarten Learners Imperative for Formal School Readiness

Karla Bianca D. Flores,* Sheena Marie B. Macabebe, Anna Marie A. Canono, Helen O. Revalde

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Motor skills development plays an integral role in preparing kindergarten learners to be ready in a formal school setting. This research assessed the motor skills of kindergarten learners toward formal school readiness. It utilized quantitative descriptive correlational research design. The study was conducted in Bonbon Elementary School, Cebu City with 25 respondents. A researcher-developed survey questionnaires were designed and utilized to gather the needed data. Employing weighted means to get the extent of readiness of the learners as perceived by the teachers and parents and an independent sample T-test in determining the significant relationship. The empirical findings revealed that most teacher respondents were females aged 27–33. They all held Early Childhood Education Degrees, some with master's units. Experienced from 2 to 10 years, with many not attending seminars in ECE while the parent respondents answered the survey questionnaires who are identified as having low monthly income and parents at a young age. The statistical test revealed that there was a significant relationship between fine motor skills and gross motor skills in teachers' and parent's assessment of the skills readiness of the learners. Based on the result, the researcher concludes that parent's support and kindergarten teachers' knowledge, skills, and understanding of what helps strengthen students' motor skills. Thus, the utilization of the enhancement plan is necessary for achieving the total development of kindergarten learners' motor skills for formal school readiness.

Keywords: *Early Childhood Education, motor skills, perceptions, quantitative*

Introduction

Recently, a child's entrance into kindergarten is a major milestone. The transition can be filled with trepidation, anticipation, eagerness and uncertainty. Some kids enter more prepared than others, with more support and more exposure to formal educational settings. Other children will have experienced nothing like it before. The shift in expectations for kindergarten education, where academic skills like reading, writing, and mathematics are increasingly emphasized, has been a topic of discussion and concern in recent years. While some argue that early exposure to academic concepts can better prepare children for later schooling, others express concerns about the potential negative impacts on young children's development.

The fundamental internal mechanisms that move the body or certain body parts in space are referred to as motor abilities. In addition to the actual motions, motor skills also comprise the thought processes that result in the movements. Perceptual motor, sensorimotor, and psychomotor skills are examples of motor-related abilities that involve sensory perception and the interaction between the movement systems (i.e., body parts) and the cognitive system. Fine motor abilities entail synchronizing small muscle movements required for tasks like drawing, writing, speaking, and playing an instrument. Gross motor skills involve the body's major muscles and are related to balance, orientation and movement of the trunk and limbs, and posture. While they are clearly related and develop together, motor skills to school performance are unclear.

Motor skill development in early childhood contributes to school readiness (Gonzalez et al., 2019). Likewise, during early childhood, motor skill development is an important aspect of children's readiness for school because having motor skills ensures that children are ready for their first years of formal schooling (McClelland & Cameron, 2019). Cheung et al. (2019), suggested that motor development occurs first and the development of 2 cognitive skills is enhanced by motor learning. Researchers suggested that there is a close relationship between children's early motor skills and later cognitive and academic abilities (Hudson & Willoughby, 2021; Klupp et al., 2021). Therefore, learning during the early years should include active learning to promote motor skill development rather than focusing solely on academics (Cheung et al., 2019).

Children need a range of skills to transition successfully to formal schooling. In early childhood classrooms, children must master their fine and gross motor skills, due to their influence on early academic achievement and cognitive skills, motor skills and physical activity (PA) may also be linked to school preparation. Moreover, the requirements for a youngster to be prepared for school include motor skills. Considering the suggested and established link between physical activity and motor abilities, it is plausible that a child's likelihood of achieving school ready may increase if their physical activity levels rise along with their motor skills. Other studies have also demonstrated an association between motor skills and academic achievement, as well as with cognitive abilities. Additionally, gross motor skills have been longitudinally associated with social behavior, self-control, cooperation and a decrease in hyperactivity in young children, while fine motor skills have been associated with academic achievement, attention and executive function. Similarly, intervention studies of preschool children show that school physical activity promotion and motor activity breaks can increase educational scores.

Problematically, many Filipino children specifically to the incoming kindergarten learners may lack school readiness due to different issues. The following factors such as, the pandemic's impact on social interactions, structured learning experiences, and high-quality

instruction. These had created huge hitches or gaps towards their learning. Furthermore, these affect the learners' motor skills development.

The problem that prompted this study is that some kindergarten learners in the public schools lack motor skills necessary for formal school readiness, and kindergarten teachers are challenged to support learners' development of motor skills needed for formal school readiness.

The assessment of prior skills of the entering kindergarten learners is a good measure of the child's ability to cope with formal schooling is needed for future learning interventions. Likewise, this study explores parents' and teachers' perspectives on kindergarten learners' motor skills necessary for formal school readiness. As such, these skills are crucial for understanding the expectations and collaboration between these two key stakeholders. The outcome of this study will somehow design a development plan that particularly addresses the motor skills that will allow the school to screen learners that may not be ready for kindergarten and will also provide feedback to the parents. Having this important information will likewise allow the school to communicate with parents about their child's motor skills capability before kindergarten. This will also help teachers when they are suggesting to parents to hold their child back for another year and not enroll them in kindergarten so early.

Research Questions

This research assessed the motor skills of the kindergarten learners towards the formal school readiness in Bonbon Elementary School, Cebu City during the academic year 2023 -2024 as a basis for a motor skills enhancement plan. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondent groups in terms of:
 - 1.1. Parent-respondents:
 - 1.1.1. age and gender,
 - 1.1.2. highest educational attainment,
 - 1.1.3. number of children in elementary, and
 - 1.1.4. combined family monthly income?
 - 1.2. Teacher-respondents:
 - 1.2.1. age and gender,
 - 1.2.2. highest educational attainment, and
 - 1.2.3. length of service?
2. As perceived by the parents and teacher's respondents, what is the extent of the skills readiness of the learners in terms of:
 - 2.1. fine motor skills, and
 - 2.2. gross motor skills?
3. Is there a significant difference between the parent's and teachers' perceptions of the motor skills of the learners?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what motor skills enhancement plan can be developed?

Literature Review

This study claimed that the total development of motor skills of kindergarten learners is essential in preparation for formal school settings.

According to Gardner (1983), individuals possess various distinct types of intelligence, rather than a single general intelligence. These types encompass areas like linguistic, logical-mathematical, musical, spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic intelligences, emphasizing a broader understanding of human capability. Those who have high bodily-kinesthetic intelligence is said to have good body mobility, action performance, and physical control are all stated to be strong points. People who thrive in this field usually have good hand-eye coordination and dexterity. Children with strong bodily-kinesthetic intelligence like moving because of this. They use movement to learn about themselves, their physical and mental capabilities, and their surroundings. These children are easily identified. Sports, gaming, building, dancing, hands-on jobs, working with scientific materials, and arts and crafts are all activities they like and excel at. These activities need precision, quickness, and physical coordination, as well as the use of their minds and fine and gross motor abilities. Multiple intelligences theory has enabled major activities and investigations, notably in the field of education, as well as a shift in educators' perspectives on the ideas of learning and intelligence (Cavas & Cavas, 2020).

As stated by Erikson (1950), there is a distinct psychological battle that occurs throughout the eight stages of a person's existence. These difficulties shape your personality throughout your life. Erikson's theory of psychosocial development has 8 distinct stages. Erikson assumes that a psychosocial crisis occurs at each stage of development. Erikson believes the psychological needs of the individual (i.e. psycho) conflict with the needs of society (i.e. social), hence the name, psychosocial. During the infancy stage of development, Erikson believes an infant must first form a loving, trusting relationship with the caregiver, or develop a sense of mistrust instead. Parents and teachers guide and support kids in the right way by identifying the many objectives, difficulties, and worries at each stage of life. Individuals go through stages as they mature and encounter new decisions and turning points during childhood,

youth, and adulthood (Orenstein & Lewis, 2022).

In addition, Bandura (1977), states that we pick up social skills by seeing and copying the actions of others. Realizing that direct reinforcement alone could not explain all forms of learning, Bandura expanded his theory to include social learning the idea that people pick up knowledge from watching others. A key component of skill development is imitation, which enables us to pick up new information quickly and effectively by observing people around us. The majority of youngsters pick up skills via seeing parents, caregivers, siblings, and peers—from interactive play to speaking to gross motor motions. The ability of a young infant to mimic the behavior of others is a crucial technique for social learning, or picking up new skills. The value of the child's imitation skills is in what they can reveal about the child's prior knowledge. Holding a pencil or crayon, for instance. There is a good chance that a child may mimic or duplicate an adult when they witness the adult holding the same object as them. Social learning theory (SLT) is frequently viewed as a bridge between behaviorism (classical learning theory) and cognitive theory (Rumjaun & Narod, 2020).

The muscle movements we employ on a daily basis are known as motor skills. They enable us to perform daily tasks like brushing our teeth and going for walks and runs. It's important to remember that motor skills are acquired; we don't naturally possess them. Rather, motor skill acquisition comes from repetition and practice. Eventually, motor skills become very accurate and need little to no effort to complete.

Since motor skills are acquired through learning, they are frequently utilized as developmental benchmarks for kids. For example, most children should be able to walk and run without any trouble by the time they are five years old. It is true that the 'critical period' for the development of motor abilities occurs between the ages of three and five. This is due to the nervous system's current state, which facilitates the learning of new abilities. The first step in assisting kids to feel independent is helping them master motor skills. Children who are secure in their gross motor abilities can make significant daily progress, such as getting out of bed and moving upstairs and downstairs.

Even though the tasks we perform with our fine motor abilities are typically modest, they can yet be very significant. Examples of such tasks include flossing our teeth and buttoning and zipping our clothing. The best way to assist kids in achieving various degrees of independence is through the development of motor skills. It can be frustrating for young children to engage in activities that call for the use of fine motor skills, such coloring or playing with toys that include smaller pieces, like puzzles. Children will be able to use a greater variety of hand manipulations as their fine motor skills improve. For example, they will be able to draw circular and cross shapes, hold crayons between two fingers and their thumb (just like an adult would), and gradually start to color and draw inside the lines or the entire coloring page.

Republic Act No. 8980 (Early Childhood Care and Development Act), entitled, "An Act Promulgating a Comprehensive Policy and a National System for Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD), Providing Funds Therefore and for Other Purposes", or the ECCD Act of 2000. Early childhood encompasses the first phase of human development from prenatal to age six (0-6). Care reflects what parents/adults are able to provide for a child—love, protection, safe and adequate environment, and time. Development refers to the four interrelated domains of child development (physical, social, emotional, and cognitive). Thus, ECCD is an integrated concept that cuts across the different disciplines and sectors and necessitates policy decisions spanning multiple agencies (health, nutrition, education, and social welfare/protection) to provide for the holistic needs of children (0-6).

ECCD addresses the rights and needs of children (0-6). Children have rights (even before birth) and families, communities, and governments (national and local) must work together for the realization of these rights. The roles and relationships of ECCD players are defined. The "child-friendly wheel" aptly illustrates ECCD as collective task, with the child (0-6) at the hub of the wheel, in keeping with the ecological perspective - the child within the context of his/her family, community, and society. This means putting the child at the core of the development agenda while strengthening and/or influencing the contexts in which are growing up.

Section 2. Declaration of Policy. - It is hereby declared the policy of the State to promote the rights of children to survival, development, and special protection with full recognition of the nature of childhood and its special needs; and to support parents in their roles as primary caregivers and as their children's first teachers. The State shall institutionalize a National System for Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) that is comprehensive, integrative and sustainable, that involves multi-sectoral and inter-agency collaboration at the national and local levels among government; among service providers, families and communities; and among the public and private sectors, nongovernment organizations, professional associations, and academic institutions, This System shall promote the inclusion of children with special needs and advocate respect for cultural diversity. It shall be anchored on complementary strategies for ECCD that include service delivery for children from conception to age six (6), educating parents and caregivers, encouraging the active involvement of parents and communities in ECCD programs, raising awareness about the importance of ECCD, and promoting community development efforts that improve the quality of life for young children and families.

Republic Act No. 10410 (Children's Emergency Relief and Protection Act) an act recognizing the age from zero (0) to eight (8) years as the first crucial stage of education development and strengthening the early childhood care and development system, appropriating funds therefor and for other purposes. It is hereby declared the policy of the State to promote the rights of children to survival, development, and special protection with full recognition of the nature of childhood and as well as the need to provide developmentally appropriate experiences to address their needs; and to support parents in their roles as primary caregivers and as their children's first

teachers. Further, the State hereby recognizes the age from zero (0) to eight (8) years as the first crucial stage of educational development of which the age from zero (0) to four (4) years shall be the responsibility of the Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) Council. Therefore, the responsibility to help develop children in the formative years between age five (5) to eight (8) years shall be with the Department of Education (DepEd). The State shall institutionalize a National System for Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) that is comprehensive, integrative, and sustainable, that involves multisectoral and interagency collaboration at the national and local levels among government; among service providers, families, and communities, and among the public and private sectors, nongovernment organizations; professional associations and academic institutions.

The System shall promote the inclusion of children with special needs, provide for reasonable accommodation and accessible environments for children with disabilities and advocate respect for cultural and linguistic diversity, including the use of Filipino Sign Language as the visual language of the deaf community. It shall be anchored on complementary strategies for ECCD that include service delivery for children from age zero (0) to four (4) years, educating parents and caregivers, encouraging the active involvement of parents and communities in ECCD programs, raising awareness about the important efforts that improve the quality of life for young children and families.

Republic Act No. 7323 (Special Program for Employment of Students) otherwise known as the Special Program for Employment of Students (SPES). R.A. No. 7323, which was passed in 1992, is an earn-and-learn program to develop productive work ethics in the youth. Stipulated under Republic Act No. 7323, known as the “Special Program for Employment of Students,” as amended by Republic Act No. 9547 and 10917, is a government initiative designed to provide temporary employment opportunities for financially challenged students to keep them in school and finish their education by allowing them to work and make their school break productive. The program aims to help students earn extra income to support their education expenses while gaining valuable work experience in various industries and agencies.

According to the Revised Integrated Manual of Operations of Special Program for the Employment of Students (SPES) 2017, since its implementation in 1993, it has been considered one of the government’s most relevant and worthwhile youth employment programs. The beneficiaries, which are the students and out-of-school youth (OSY) will be exposed to the real world of work, where they will gain experience and enhance their capabilities as future members of the workforce. Through this program, it is expected that it will effectively hone their skills, attitudes, and habits toward work.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilizes a non-experimental, quantitative descriptive correlational research design that tries to explain the relationship between the respondents’ profiles and the extent of the skills readiness of the learners in terms of fine motor skills and gross motor skills. Descriptive correlational design is employed in research investigations that attempt to present a static picture of situations while also establishing a relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009). This includes parents and teacher respondents from kindergarten by providing them with the survey questionnaires. This likewise includes collecting and analyzing data to see if there is a link between them.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the parents and teachers, while the subjects of the study are the kindergarten learners for the school year 2023-2024. Parents and teachers are the respondents since they are the most knowledgeable about the subject. In determining the respondents, two factors were considered first the number of teachers handling kindergarten and the active parents of the learners. In ensuring the validity and reliability of the samples, simple random sampling was utilized. Hence, 25 respondents are identified.

Instrument

This research used the research-made survey questionnaire. Researcher-made questionnaire denotes the instrument to be used crafted by the researchers. The questionnaire was personally crafted by the researchers validated by the experts and assessed by colleagues in academe to ensure its validity. The contents are primarily based on the information shared by the researchers intended by both parents and teachers in which the inventory consists of statements describing the readiness of the child in terms of their motor skills. A Likert scale of the level of readiness was used to measure the motor skills of the kindergarten learners. The instrument assessed the extent of motor skills readiness of the learners and scaled to four levels. A scale of (4) implies Extremely Ready; (3) denotes Ready; (2) indicates Somewhat Ready; and (1) suggests Not Ready.

There are two instruments used for teacher-respondents and parent—respondents. The instrument was composed of two parts. For teacher-respondents, part one is a set of questions that determine the profile of the respondents as to their age, marital status, highest educational attainment, and number of years in teaching. Part two is the set statements describing the readiness of the learner in terms of their gross motor and fine motor skills. For parents—respondents, part one is a set of questions that determine the profile of the respondents as to their age, marital status, highest educational attainment, number of children in the family, and combined family income. Part two is the set statements describing the appropriate level of readiness of their child in terms of their gross motor and fine

motor skills.

Procedure

The researcher wrote a transmittal letter asking for approval to conduct the study to the identified respondents of the study and sent it to the school principal. Upon approval, the researcher then administered the survey. Since physical classes have resumed in the country, administration and collection of data were done face-to-face. The researcher gives the survey questionnaires to 5 teachers and 20 parents. After the data has been submitted back to the researchers, the researcher checks individual questionnaires for completeness of data entries. With the help of a Data Matrix file, the researcher encoded each data using the said file. After this, data hygiene was conducted to ensure all entries were consistent and complete. Statistical software was used in tabulating and analyzing the gathered data. Based on the results, statistical interpretation was then supported with professional recognition when representing significant results, conclusions, and actions.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that the respondents' confidentiality was respected and maintained in the conduct of the study. The researcher advised the respondents to fill out the consent form before they began answering the survey questionnaires. The consent form's concept is that the researchers provided the respondents with enough information regarding the study that allowed the respondents to be informed about their benefits when participating in the study. Also, this assured the respondents that only authorized personnel have access to all the information acquired and retrieved from the respondents.

This research has ethical implications for addressing and promoting the search for knowledge and truth by preventing data fabrication or falsification. To avoid such hazards, the participants in this study are informed of everything they need to know about the study's purpose, duration, and process. It is entirely up to them whether they choose to participate in this study. The respondents were not forced to participate in the study if they did not want to. If, for any reason, the respondents may withdraw from the investigation. There will be no pressure on the respondents to continue. There will be no negative consequences if respondents decline or withdraw from the study. Throughout the survey procedures, the researchers complied with the ethical research considerations. The researchers kept all respondents' sensitive information and identities protected.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data which were the researchers, analyzed and interpreted to the specific objectives of the study. The following are the data presented in this section. Profile of the respondents, degree of Parental Roles of the Respondents, and test of a significant relationship. The respondents answered the questionnaires conducted randomly in Bonbon Elementary School.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Age and Gender of the Parent-Respondents

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
36-42	1	5.00	1	5.00	2	10.00
29-35	9	45.00	3	15.00	12	60.00
22-28	5	25.00	1	5.00	6	30.00
Total	15	75.00	5	25.00	20	100.00

This study includes the age and gender of the parents-respondents, highest educational attainment, number of children in elementary, and combined family monthly income and the work profile of the respondents. These were gathered through the questionnaire by 20 respondents.

Parents-Respondents

Age and Gender

Age and gender of the parents-respondents are considered important variables that need to be determined in this study which could help in explaining the results of the study. Data gathered are presented in Table 1 below.

As seen in table 1, 5 out of 20 were male who compromised 25% of the total respondents. There were 15 female respondents which composed 75% of the total respondents.

Table 2 presents, 1 were 36-42 for female or 5%, and 1 male for 36-42 years old or 5% a total of 2 or 10%, and 9 were female for 29-35 years old or 45% and 3 for male or 15% a total of 12 or 60%, and 5 were female for 22-28 years old or 25% and 1 for male or 5% a total of 6 or 30%.

Parental participation was more strongly influenced by their educational level, age, occupation, and marital status (Naite, 2021). Thus, the high involvement of the parents can significantly contribute to the development of academic performance and motor skills of kindergarten learners.

Educational Attainment

Table 2. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Parent-Respondents*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
College Graduate	5	25.00
College Level	4	20.00
High School Graduate	4	20.00
High School Level	4	20.00
Elementary Graduate	1	5.00
Elementary Level	2	10.00
Total	20	100.00

As presented in Table 2, among the 20 respondents, 5 of them graduated in college or 20%, 4 of them were college level or 20%, 4 of them graduated high school or 20%, 4 of them were high school level or 20%, 1 of them graduated in elementary or 5%, 2 of them were elementary level or 10%. This indicated that 25% percent of the respondents are professionals and 75% percent are non-professionals. Hence, more respondents were non-professionals than professionals.

This means that most parents choose early parenthood over returning to school to finish their education. Because of the features of early motherhood, the consequences may be worse: pregnancy is more usually unexpected, the family unit is seldom established at development, and the young parents are at an important turning point in their lives (Jojansen & Nielsen, 2019). Finances and mental health are significant concerns. As a result, schooling is delayed so that young parents can cope better.

Number of Children in the Family

Table 3. *Parent-Respondents' Number of Children in Elementary*

<i>Number of Children in Elementary</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
5 and up	1	5.00
3-4	5	25.00
1-2	14	70.00
Total	20	100.00

As shown in Table 3, among the 20 respondents, 1 out of 20 respondents have five and up children or 5%, and five of them have three to four children or 25%, and 14 of them have one to two children or 70%.

In the study of Shao et al. (2022) they concluded that the number of children in a family had a stronger moderating influence on the relationship between parental involvement and parent satisfaction than families with fewer children. Parents shouldn't worry about the impact of additional children on other children's education, but they must not disregard tutoring and assistance for their children due to the huge number of children.

Combined Family Income

Table 4. *Parent-Respondents' Combined Family Monthly Income*

<i>Monthly Income (in pesos)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Above 30,000	1	5.00
25,001-30,000	1	5.00
20,001-25,000	1	5.00
15,001-20,000	1	5.00
10,001-15,000	4	20.00
10,000 and below	12	60.00
Total	20	100.00

As presented in Table 4, 1 out of 20 respondents was earning 30,000 and above or 5%, 1 of them was earning 25,001- to 30,000 or 5%, 1 of them was earning 15,0001 to 20,000 or 5%, four of them were earning 10,001 to 15,000 or 20% and twelve of them were earning 10,000 below or 60%.

According to Peconcillo et al. (2020), students with greater socioeconomic status outperform middle-class students, who then outperform students with lower socioeconomic statuses. In contrast to this conclusion, it is vital to realize that academic achievement is influenced by a variety of factors other than socioeconomic status. While economic status clearly influences educational achievements, it is unduly simple to assume that it is the single driver of academic achievement.

Profile of the Teachers- Respondents

This study includes the age and gender of the teachers-respondents, highest educational attainment, and length of service. These were

gathered through the questionnaire by 5 respondents.

Parents-Respondents

Age and Gender

Teachers' age and gender are regarded as important criteria that must be identified in this study in order to help explain the study's findings. Table 5 summarizes the information gathered.

Table 5. Age and Gender of the Teacher-Respondents

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
31-33	1	20.00	0	0.00	1	20.00
28-30	2	40.00	0	0.00	2	40.00
25-27	2	40.00	0	0.00	2	40.00
Total	5	100.00	0	0.00	5	100.00

Table 5 presented the respondent type of age and gender and the respondents are all female who comprised 100% of the total respondents. Table 5 displays, 1 of them were 31 to 33 years old or 20%, and two of them were 28 to 30 years or 40%, and two was 25 to 27 years old or 40%. According to Topchyan and Woehler (2021), female teachers were more involved with their students than male teachers and substitute teachers. Teachers play pivotal roles in creating environments that nurture children’s development and learning through positive interactions and age-appropriate instructions.

Educational Attainment

It is thought crucial to know the educational attainment of the teachers to assist in comprehending the study's findings. Table 6 displays the collected data.

Table 6. Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	f	%
With Master's Units	3	60.00
Bachelor's Degree	2	40.00
Total	5	100.00

As shown in Table 6, among the 5 respondents three of them with master’s units or 60% and 2 of them was bachelor’s degree or 40%. This indicated that 60% of the respondents earned with master’s units and 40% was bachelor’s degrees.

Lee and Lee (2020), stress that students who were taught by several highly qualified teachers were more likely to achieve higher-level educational degrees. Teachers' achievement of higher degrees, particularly master's degrees, has received substantial attention, as many states grant compensation increases for teachers who get additional education. Teacher qualification will continue to play an integral role in developing every learner's total development.

Length of Service

The length of employment of instructors is viewed as a critical factor that must be demonstrated for this study to explain its findings. Table 7 summarizes the information gathered.

Table 7. Length of Service of Teacher-Respondents

Length of Service (in years)	f	%
6-10	1	20.00
1-5	4	80.00
Total	5	100.00

As seen in Table 7, among the five respondents one of them were in six to 10 years in service or 20% and four was in one to five years in service or 80%. This indicated that 80% of the respondents are have more experienced and encountered different behaviors and skills that already developed during their first to fifth year in service. Hence, 20% are in six to ten years in service.

Podolsky and Darling-Hammond (2019), found out that teaching experience is positively associated with student achievement gains throughout a teacher's career; as teachers gain experience, their students are more likely to perform better on measures of success other than test scores; teachers improve their effectiveness when they teach in a supportive, collegial environment or accumulate experience in the same grade, subject, or district; and more experienced teachers benefit their colleagues.

Extent of Skills Readiness of the Learner’s Fine Motor Skills as Perceived by the Parents

Table 8. The extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners in terms of Fine Motor Skills as perceived by the Parents

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
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1	Uses all five fingers to get food/toys placed on a flat surface	3.70	Extremely Ready
2	Picks up objects with thumb and index finger	3.35	Extremely Ready
3	Displays a definite hand preference	3.30	Extremely Ready
4	Puts small objects in/out of containers	3.20	
5	Holds crayon with all the fingers of his hand making a fist (i.e., pal mar grasp)	3.40	Extremely Ready
6	Unscrews the lid of a container or unwraps food	3.10	Ready
7	Scribbles spontaneously	3.20	Ready
8	Scribbles vertical and horizontal lines	3.35	Extremely Ready
9	Draws circle purposefully	3.50	Extremely Ready
10	Draws a human figure (head, eyes, trunk, arms, hands/fingers)	3.70	Extremely Ready
11	Draws a house using geometric forms	3.30	Extremely Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.37	Extremely Ready

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Extremely Ready; 2.50-3.24-Ready; 1.75-2.49 – Somewhat Ready; 1.00-1.74- Not Ready

As shown in the Table 8, The parents are extremely ready that the learners uses all five fingers to get food/toys placed on a flat surface, picks up objects with thumb and index finger, displays a definite hand preference, puts small objects in/out of containers, holds crayon with all the fingers of his hand making a fist, and ready to unscrews the lid of a container or unwraps food and scribbles spontaneously, extremely ready to scribbles vertical and horizontal lines, draws a human figure (head, eyes, trunks, arms, hand/fingers), and draws a house using geometric forms. Table 8 shows that the respondents are extremely ready with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.37.

Fisher et al. (2018) found that fine motor skills directly influence children's academics and recommended more research in greater detail about how fine motor skills relate to specific academic skills related to numeracy. He suggested that structured play during early childhood education can support gross and fine motor skills development. Based on local data, there is evidence that some kindergarten students need more engagement in motor skills which is necessary for formal school readiness.

Extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners' Fine Motor Skills as Perceived by the Teachers

This was the Skills Readiness of the Learners in terms of fine motor skills as perceived by the Teachers. The indicators and the verbal description are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. *The extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners in terms of Fine Motor Skills as perceived by the Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses all five fingers to get food/toys placed on a flat surface	4.00	Extremely Ready
2	Picks up objects with thumb and index finger	4.00	Extremely Ready
3	Displays a definite hand preference	4.00	Extremely Ready
4	Puts small objects in/out of containers	4.00	Extremely Ready
5	Holds crayon with all the fingers of his hand making a fist (i.e., pal mar grasp)	2.80	Ready
6	Unscrews the lid of a container or unwraps food	3.60	Extremely Ready
7	Scribbles spontaneously	4.00	Extremely Ready
8	Scribbles vertical and horizontal lines	4.00	Extremely Ready
9	Draws circle purposefully	4.00	Extremely Ready
10	Draws a human figure (head, eyes, trunk, arms, hands/fingers)	3.80	Extremely Ready
11	Draws a house using geometric forms	3.80	Extremely Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.82	Extremely Ready

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Extremely Ready; 2.50-3.24-Ready; 1.75-2.49 – Somewhat Ready; 1.00-1.74- Not Ready

Presented in the Table 9, The teachers are extremely ready that the learners uses all five fingers to get food/toys placed on a flat surface, picks up objects with thumb and index finger, displays a definite hand preference, puts small objects in/out of containers, and ready to hold a crayon with all the fingers of his hand making a fist, extremely ready to unscrews the lid of a container or unwraps food, scribbles spontaneously, scribbles vertical and horizontal lines, draws a human figure (head, eyes, trunks, arms, hand/fingers), and draws a house using geometric forms. Table 9 shows that the respondents are extremely ready with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.82.

In the study of Suggate et al. (2019), they highlighted the importance of childhood activities in early childhood classrooms for children's motor skill development, such as using manipulatives, dressing dolls, cutting, drawing, etc., because they enhance children's school readiness. Furthermore, fine motor skills contribute to students' overall readiness for school and include daily school tasks such as holding a pencil, opening and closing markers, buttoning and unbuttoning clothes.

This was the skills readiness of the learner's gross motor skills perceived by parents. The indicators and verbal descriptions are shown in Table 10.

As shown in Table 10, the respondents are extremely ready with the weighted mean of 3.25 – 3.55, that the learners could climbs on chair or other elevated piece of furniture like bed without help, move body part as directed, jumps up, jumps and turn, dances patterns/ joins group movement activities and ready with weighted mean of 2.85 – 3.15 that the learners can walks backwards, runs without tripping or falling, walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step with one hand held, walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step, walks upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail, walks downstairs with alternate feet

without holding onto a handrail, throws ball overhead with direction. Table 10 shows that the respondents are ready with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.14.

Table 10. *The extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners in terms of Gross Motor Skills as perceived by the Parents*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Climbs on chair or other elevated piece of furniture like a bed without help.	3.40	Extremely Ready
2	Walks backwards	3.00	Ready
3	Runs without tripping or falling.	2.85	Ready
4	Walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step with one hand held.	2.95	Ready
5	Walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step.	2.75	Ready
6	Walks upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail	3.15	Ready
7	Walks upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail.	3.15	Ready
8	Walks downstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail	2.95	Ready
9	Moves body part as Directed.	3.35	Extremely Ready
10	Jumps up	3.25	Extremely Ready
11	Throws ball overhead with direction	3.10	Ready
12	Hops one to three steps on preferred foot	3.15	Ready
13	Jumps and turns	3.30	Extremely Ready
14	Dances patterns/joins group movement activities	3.55	Extremely Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.14	Ready

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Extremely Ready; 2.50-3.24-Ready; 1.75-2.49 – Somewhat Ready; 1.00-1.74- Not Ready

According to Newell (2020), he investigated what makes some motor skills fundamental. This researcher found that Fundamental Motor Skills consist of three conditions: uniqueness to the movement pattern/outcomes, the universality of the functional outcome amongst the healthy population, and the capacity to act as an antecedent influence supporting the generalization of sets of motor skills.

Extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners Gross Motor Skills as Perceived by the Teachers

This was the skills readiness of the learner's gross motor skills perceived by teachers. The indicators and verbal descriptions are shown in Table 11.

Table 11. *The extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners in terms of Gross Motor Skills as perceived by the Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Climbs on chair or other elevated piece of furniture like a bed without help.	4.00	Extremely Ready
2	Walks backwards	3.40	Extremely Ready
3	Runs without tripping or falling.	3.80	Extremely Ready
4	Walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step with one hand held.	3.60	Extremely Ready
5	Walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step.	3.00	Ready
6	Walks upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail	3.80	Extremely Ready
7	Walks upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail.	3.20	Ready
8	Walks downstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail	3.40	Extremely Ready
9	Moves body part as Directed.	4.00	Extremely Ready
10	Jumps up	4.00	Extremely Ready
11	Throws ball overhead with direction	4.00	Extremely Ready
12	Hops one to three steps on preferred foot	4.00	Extremely Ready
13	Jumps and turns	3.80	Extremely Ready
14	Dances patterns/joins group movement activities	3.80	Extremely Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.70	Extremely Ready

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Extremely Ready; 2.50-3.24-Ready; 1.75-2.49 – Somewhat Ready; 1.00-1.74- Not Ready

Shown in Table 11, the respondents extremely ready with weighted mean of 3.40 – 4.00 that the learners could climbs on chair or other elevated piece of furniture like bed without help, walks backwards, runs without tripping or falling, walks upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step with one hand held, walks downstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail, moves body part as directed, jumps up, throws ball overhead with direction, hops one to three steps on preferred foot, jumps and turns, dance patterns/joins group movement activities, and ready with the weighted mean of 3.00 – 3.20 that the learners can walk upstairs holding onto a handrail, two feet on each step and walk upstairs with alternate feet without holding onto a handrail. Table 11 shows that the respondents are extremely ready with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.70.

According to Newell (2020), he investigated what makes some motor skills fundamental. This researcher found that Fundamental Motor Skills consist of three conditions: uniqueness to the movement pattern/outcomes, the universality of the functional outcome amongst the healthy population, and the capacity to act as an antecedent influence supporting the generalization of sets of motor skills.

Summary on the Extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners

This was the extent of skills readiness of the learners. The table 12 shown the components, parents verbal description and teachers verbal description based of the questionnaires made by the researchers.

Table 12. Summary on the Extent of Skills Readiness of the Learners

Components	Parents		Teachers	
	WM	Verbal Description	WM	Verbal Description
Fine Motor Skills	3.37	Extremely Ready	3.82	Extremely Ready
Gross Motor Skills	3.14	Ready	3.70	Extremely Ready
Grand Mean	3.26	Extremely Ready	3.76	Extremely Ready

Table 12 presented, fine motor skills with weighted mean of 3.37 for parents verbal description and 3.82 for teachers verbal description are extremely ready both for parents and teachers' respondents. Gross motor skills with weighted mean of 3.14 for parents verbal description are ready and 3.70 for teachers verbal description are extremely ready for teachers' respondents. The total grand mean is 3.26 for parents-respondents and 3.76 for teachers-respondents and extremely ready for both parents and teachers respondents.

According to Gonzalez et al. (2019), motor skill development includes both gross motor skills (large muscle movements like sitting independently) and fine motor skills (small muscle movements like writing). Primarily, motor skills are an essential part of cognitive development and are necessary for brain development. Motor development relates to social-emotional development as motor development is associated with a child's social skills, which influence their ability to make friends and have positive behavioral outcomes when interacting with others.

Significant Difference Between the Teachers and Parents' Assessment on the Skills Readiness of the Learners

The level of a significant between the teachers and parents' assessment on the skills readiness of the learners was considered.

Table 13. Test of significant difference between the teachers and parents' assessment on the skills readiness of the learners

Variables	Source of Difference	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	Comp. t- value	p-value	Decision	Result
Fine Motor Skills	Parents	37.10	5.57	-4.90	-3.265	0.004	Reject Ho	S
	Teachers	42.00	1.87					
Gross Motor Skills	Parents	43.90	9.94	-7.90	-2.607	0.020	Reject Ho	S
	Teachers	51.80	4.60					

*significant at $p < 0.05$; NS = Not Significant; S = Significant

Table 13 showed the test of difference between the teachers and parents' assessment on the skills readiness of the learners. This was tested at 0.000 and 0.001 level of significance using a two-tailed test. Since the computed p-value of 0.000 and 0.001 means that there was a significant relationship between fine motor skills and gross motor skills on teacher's and parents' assessment of the skills readiness of the learners. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. In the study of Pranoto et al. (2021), they found out that children need to master their motor skills because it creates the foundation for performing movement skills and the foundation for further movement development.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the role of parents and teachers as a part of the microsystem and mesosystem make up the children's surroundings. Their parenting techniques and teacher's skills most likely have an impact on the kids' developmental results, especially the growth of their motor abilities. The developed motor skills of kindergarten learners can significantly play a big factor in their readiness in formal school settings. Thus, promoting and enhancing very kindergarten learners' motor skills is necessary in preparing them for formal school settings. Following the study's findings, it is highly recommended that the self-help skills enhancement plan be implemented and adopted in developing the motor skills of kindergarten learners.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Karla Bianca D. Flores

Bonbon Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Sheena Marie B. Macabebe

Candiis Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Anna Marie A. Canono

Sagbayan Central Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Dr. Helen O. Revalde

Cebu Technological University – Philippines